

A method for national scientific competitiveness evaluation based on high contribution authors

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Abstract

Scientometrics is a beneficial instrument to observe and analyze a country's scientific research performance based on scientific publications. Since its launch in 2016, the Nature Index has provided a measure of national/institutional high-quality research productivity in the natural sciences, garnering extensive attention from the scientific community and the media. Our study proposes a novel method to gauge the scientific research competitiveness of leading nations from a state-dominated perspective. Using the publication data (2012–2021) from 82 journals embodied in Nature Index, we explored the practice of research leadership, impact, and collaboration based on the contributions of the first authors and corresponding authors. The findings reveal that the international research collaboration of leading countries has expanded considerably during the previous decade. Regarding research impact, the United States and Japan are on a similar declining pattern, which has a positive association with leadership, while for Germany, the United Kingdom, and France, research impact and leadership exhibit a U-shaped connection. Furthermore, while China's research leadership has steadily increased in recent years, the scale of international collaboration and research impact has been in a declining pattern.

Introduction

In recent years, international science activities have shown a puzzling phenomenon. As the national academic influence extended through the implementation of ongoing scientific cooperation, international collaboration has taken place all over the world (Narula, 2003). However, the expansion of international cooperation often accompanies increased scientific competition. Several scientific and technological indicators, such as Nature Index (NI) and Essential Science Indicators (ESI), repeatedly emphasize national competitiveness in production and impact, which may be antithetical to international collaboration.

Scientometric evaluation methods have been widely applied in national scientific performance comparison. The growth of international research cooperation has made it increasingly difficult to measure the actual impact of national effects in scientometric analysis (Bornmann et al., 2018). Nevertheless, this did not affect the irrational practice of allocating the share of international co-authored papers (Marginson, 2021). Consider the case of Nature Index, for example. Although the Nature Index is widely recognized by the international research community in evaluating the national and institutional performance, there are still two limitations: (1) the contribution of authors is not differentiated, ignoring the outstanding contribution of the first and corresponding authors; (2) the contribution of countries with large numbers of researchers and large institutions has been overstated.

In this study, we improved the calculation of the NI, analyzed the leadership roles of the leading nations, and explored the cooperative and citation practices in international scientific papers based on Bibliometrics. Specifically, we seek to answer the following questions:

- (1) Regarding international research leadership, what is the pattern of the top countries with the highest publishing rate?
- (2) What is the distribution of national scientific impact reflected in citations of state-dominated papers? How does the relationship between scientific impact and national leadership vary across countries?

(3) What is the relationship between state-dominated collaboration and leadership? Does country variation exist?

Upon answering the three questions, the discussion will be carried out.

Literature review

Bibliometric-based international research evaluation

Benefiting from the advanced transportation and communication systems, as well as the developed economy, the explosive growth of international scientific research has been observed in the past decades, which has brought profound change to the country-level research evaluation. There are two primary strategies for international literature on evaluation—— qualitative and quantitative (Mattedi & Spiess, 2017).

Qualitative methods are mainly based on peer review. However, with the excessive increase in the scientific literature in recent years, both the effectiveness of peer review in the quality control of papers as well as the subjectivity and conflict of interest of peer reviewers are growing criticism (Manchikanti et al., 2015). In contrast, the quantitative method has gained increasing ground with the development of bibliometrics in scientific research evaluation, with the number of publications, journal impact, and citation patterns becoming the basic units of analysis for this evaluation procedure (Bach et al., 2011). Because of its transparency and verifiability in the statistical process, the bibliometric-based evaluation method has gradually become an efficient supplement for peer review in recruitment, funding policy, and national/institutional evaluation (Mattedi & Spiess, 2017).

Bibliometric-based evaluation activities in academic literature typically pay close attention to the two topics of productivity and quality, namely, the contribution of individual/institution/country in literature quantity is calculated to evaluate its productivity, and the quality of papers is evaluated by citation patterns and journal impact (Wu & Djurovic, 2018). Literature on bibliometric-based international research evaluation are found to explore the leadership, the partnership, and the impact of funding in international collaboration (Cai et al., 2019; Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019; González-Alcaide et al., 2017; Liu & Huang, 2022; Liu et al., 2015; Wu & Djurovic, 2018; Zhou et al., 2020). Notably, international academic leadership emphasizes the capability of countries to play a dominant or leading role in international scientific competitiveness. Despite lacking a recognized standard for evaluating leadership in scientific work, leadership has generally been measured by the number of researches published in the affiliation of the first authors' country or corresponding authors' country.

Authors contribution in academic literature

Scientific research achievements are frequently evaluated based on journal impact factors and the level of contribution by each author (Ueda et al., 2021). In most disciplines, individual research contribution is usually reflected by the authors' order in publications (Ueda et al., 2021). Allocation of thesis contributions via authorship, where researchers and their affiliated countries and geographical regions are acknowledged for their research activities, thereby demonstrating their research capacity (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019).

In 1996, Rennie et al. proposed the concept of “contributorship model”, pointing out that the specific contribution of each author should be systematically recorded (Rennie et al., 1997), which opened new channels for authorship and byline practices. This suggestion was quickly adopted primarily by high-impact biomedical journals and gradually popularized in other

research areas. Although disciplinary differences are manifested in authorship practices, we generally observe that the first and corresponding authors make the greatest contributions in most of the research areas when compared to the other authors (Júnior et al., 2017; Riesenber & Lundberg, 1990; Wren et al., 2007). However, there is still considerable controversy over the primacy of the first author and corresponding author.

In the 1990s, the first author was generally regarded as the chief executant, particularly in biomedical fields (Riesenber & Lundberg, 1990; Yank & Rennie, 1999), while corresponding authors were second only to the first author (Wren et al., 2007), and most of them were senior authors whose names appear lastly on the author byline (Drenth, 1998). This standpoint has been substantiated over the next three decades, with a plurality of literature manifesting the unanimous conclusion that first authors and corresponding authors are contributing to a higher proportion of tasks than other contributors (Júnior et al., 2017; Larivière et al., 2016; Mattsson et al., 2011; Sauermann & Haeussler, 2017), and first authors carry out more liability in research activity than corresponding authors (Júnior et al., 2017; Peidu, 2019).

It is noteworthy that many studies have emphasized the important status of corresponding authors. The corresponding author is considered to have made the greatest research contribution to connecting and coordinating among the co-authors, complying with the research ethics and authorship practices (Clement, 2014; Mattsson et al., 2011; McNutt et al., 2018; Ueda et al., 2021), and communicating with the journal during the manuscript submission, peer review, and publication process. They have ensured the research activity going smoothly and successfully to a certain extent. Therefore, some researchers argued that corresponding authors own an equal contribution status with the first author, or even their contribution exceeds that of the first author (Peidu, 2019; Ueda et al., 2021).

The research leadership based on authors' contributions reported in previous studies could be classified into three categories (González-Alcaide et al., 2017; Liu & Huang, 2022; Liu et al., 2015; Wu & Djurovic, 2018):

- (1) The number of articles published by the signatory country that is both the first author and corresponding author;
- (2) The number of articles published in the signed country of the first author;
- (3) The number of articles published in the signed country of the corresponding author.

To sum up, the above suggestions revealed the important role of authorship in the authors' contributions: the first author and the corresponding author had also become the reference basis for this study to define the patterns of individual and country/ geographical region research leadership.

Impact of international competition on scientific collaboration

As one of the significant channels for scholarly communication, academic collaboration has effectively promoted knowledge dissemination and scientific research innovation. The production of discovery and dissemination of knowledge has been further accelerated with the rapid development of internet communication technology, and scientific cooperation is gradually reforming towards globalization. International collaboration is associated with greater scientific impact has been confirmed in several studies (Arunachalam & Doss, 2000; Foley & Della Sala, 2014; Narin et al., 1991; Schmoch & Schubert, 2008; Van Raan, 1998), implying that the dominance and leadership in research activities of country-level are positively correlated with scientific cooperative status (Cimini et al., 2016; Kong et al., 2019; Mihăilă, 2018).

With the aggravation of the uncertainty of the global economy, international scientific collaboration gradually fell into a dilemma. We have observed that developing countries with low-income are palpably in an inferior position in collaborative research activities (Bai & Liu, 2016). Meanwhile, newly-emerging developing countries such as China, Brazil, South Korea, South Africa, and India are facing a bottleneck in scientific cooperation, as their rapidly developing technology challenges the leadership of Europe and the United States (Gui et al., 2019).

The strategies for maintaining scientific competitiveness in high-tech industries have been adopted by most countries in recent years, such as the “National Strategy for Critical and Emerging Technologies” released by the White House in October 2020. Moreover the “Emerging Economic Powerhouse” has worked to establish the new rules and practices to retain their scientific and technological edge and seize the opportunities that technological advance present in rapid succession (Sepehrdoust et al., 2021). This phenomenon has continued to upgrade and aggravated the tense situation of scientific collaboration, and developing countries have to seek new footholds in emerging technology research activities.

Methodology

Data collection

Research publication data was retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection. Only 82 journals embodied in NI were retrieved in the analyses because it brings together the mainstream high-quality natural-science journals of reference for their visibility and impact at an international level. We combined field tags in the Advanced Search to identify a research article’s information, including publication year and ISSN/eISSN. The document type of all the collections is “article”, and the collections include all papers published between 2012 and 2021. Six major producers of science (the United States, China, Germany, the United Kingdom, France, and Japan) were considered.

706,780 pieces of bibliographic data were downloaded from the Web of Science database. For data cleaning, if an affiliated country could not be determined, the corresponding data would then be excluded. Finally, valid data of 706,753 articles were acquired, of which 312,007 were multinational authorship papers and 69,377 had first and corresponding authors from different countries.

Indicators obtained and concepts used in the study

Contribution and leadership in research activities

We extracted the information contained in the fields for institutional affiliation and corresponding author, identifying the countries and geographic regions mentioned in the specified fields. The first and corresponding authors’ countries are taken into account for calculating leadership because of their significant positions in the article, and all other countries are deemed non-leading countries. In the case of a paper with multiple first authors or corresponding authors, we only consider the first-ranked author. The maximum combined credit for any article is 1.0, and the first author and the corresponding author equally allocated this credit. For each of the countries analyzed, the fractional credits of each article in the same country were added and formed that country’s share, and Leadership was determined as the degree of each country’s share to the total credit. Briefly, the calculation method can be described by formula (1).

$$Leadership = \frac{0.5 \times N_f + 0.5 \times N_c}{1.0 \times N_t} \quad (1)$$

In the equation, N_f represents the number of outputs in a country with only the first author's affiliation, N_c expresses the volume of papers from that country simply as corresponding author's affiliation. N_t is the total number of valid publications in 82 journals that year.

Impact of papers based on leadership

Secondly, we analyzed the degree of citation in the included papers, tying it to the concept of leadership. We first calculated an impact score defined as the average degree of citations per paper for each country per year, based on the significant role of the first author and the corresponding author. The impact score of each country was normalized by the average citations of all papers published in the same year to obtain the Impact of Papers based on Leadership (IPL) (see formula (2)). When the IPL is above 1, it means that the country's research impact is above the world average; when it is below 1, it means the opposite.

$$IPL = \frac{\sum(0.5 \times C_f + 0.5 \times C_c)/(N_f + N_c)}{\sum_{i=1}^t C_i/N_t} \quad (2)$$

In this equation, C_f is the citation frequency of papers in a country with only the first author's affiliation, and C_c indicates the cited frequency of publications in that country just as corresponding author affiliation. $\sum_{i=1}^t C_i$ represents the sum of all effective papers' citation frequencies in 82 journals. The detailed explanations of N_f , N_c , and N_t are shown in formula (1).

International collaboration based on leadership

Our approach simplifies the author to the first author and corresponding author. Therefore, the definition of international cooperation involved in the paper has been limited, which means that the first author and the corresponding author do not from the same country. The concept of International Collaboration based on Leadership (ICL) was described as the proportion of the number of cooperative articles in the total number of articles published in that country as a first or corresponding author affiliation.

$$ICL = \frac{N_f + N_c}{N_f + N_c + (N_f \cap N_c)} \quad (3)$$

In the formula, $N_f \cap N_c$ indicates the volume of papers in a country affiliated with both the first and corresponding author, and the definitions of N_f and N_c are detailed in equation (1).

Statistical test of correlation and difference based on country level

For a detailed comparison of the relativity in Leadership, IPL, and ICL between the national groups analyzed, we applied the Pearson's correlation test (each dual variable follows a linear correlation and the normal distribution) or Spearman correlation analysis. And one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was calculated for the country-level difference between the three indicators. We used Welch ANOVA and Games-Howell test when the assumption of homogeneity of variance and null hypothesis in ANOVA were rejected to determine differences between the country groups, establishing a significance level of 5%. All data will be analyzed with respect to the normality of distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk test. When the data deviates from the normal distribution seriously, we also employed the Kruskal-Wallis H test for comparative analysis among countries.

Results

Annual leadership trends related to papers

The analysis of the Leadership exercised by country groups in terms of their relative contributions to the overall number of signatures and their presence as first and/or corresponding authors. The top 6 countries with the highest degree of Leadership are presented in Figure 1, which illustrates the predominance of European and American countries such as the US, Germany, the UK, and France in the past 10 years. It can be noted from Figure 1 that the USA had the highest degree of leadership, accounting for 0.36 in 2012 and 0.27 in 2021, followed by China (0.23), Germany (0.07), the UK (0.06), Japan (0.04), and France (0.03).

Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that, notwithstanding the substantial increase of papers reported in the NI in most countries, the dominance of countries besides China has declined to vary degrees over the past decade. France had the highest decline in the Leadership degree (31%), followed by Japan (28%) and the USA (25%), While among the 6 nations, China had an increase of 150%.

Figure 1. Trends of research leadership in different countries (2012-2021)

Table 1 Multiple comparisons of leadership by country group based on ANOVA

<i>Descriptives</i>		<i>Multiple Comparisons</i>						
		<i>Dependent Variable: Leadership</i>						
<i>(I) Country</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>(J) Country</i>	<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>	
							<i>Lower Bound</i>	<i>Upper Bound</i>
USA	0.31	0.0316	China	0.16	0.0179	0.000	0.10	0.22
			Germany	0.23	0.0101	0.000	0.20	0.27

			UK	0.25	0.0100	0.000	0.21	0.28
			France	0.27	0.0101	0.000	0.24	0.31
			Japan	0.26	0.0101	0.000	0.22	0.30
China	0.15	0.0468	USA	-0.16	0.0179	0.000	-0.22	-0.10
			Germany	0.07	0.0149	0.007	0.02	0.13
			UK	0.09	0.0148	0.002	0.04	0.14
			France	0.11	0.0149	0.000	0.06	0.16
			Japan	0.10	0.0149	0.001	0.05	0.15
Germany	0.08	0.0042	USA	-0.23	0.0101	0.000	-0.27	-0.20
			China	-0.07	0.0149	0.007	-0.13	-0.02
			UK	0.01	0.0017	0.000	0.01	0.02
			France	0.04	0.0021	0.000	0.03	0.04
			Japan	0.03	0.0022	0.000	0.02	0.03
UK	0.07	0.0035	USA	-0.25	0.0100	0.000	-0.28	-0.21
			China	-0.09	0.0148	0.002	-0.14	-0.04
			Germany	-0.01	0.0017	0.000	-0.02	-0.01
			France	0.02	0.0019	0.000	0.02	0.03
			Japan	0.01	0.0020	0.000	0.01	0.02
France	0.04	0.0051	USA	-0.27	0.0101	0.000	-0.31	-0.24
			China	-0.11	0.0149	0.000	-0.16	-0.06
			Germany	-0.04	0.0021	0.000	-0.04	-0.03
			UK	-0.02	0.0019	0.000	-0.03	-0.02
			Japan	-0.01	0.0023	0.002	-0.02	0.00
Japan	0.05	0.0054	USA	-0.26	0.0101	0.000	-0.30	-0.22
			China	-0.10	0.0149	0.001	-0.15	-0.05
			Germany	-0.03	0.0022	0.000	-0.03	-0.02
			UK	-0.01	0.0020	0.000	-0.02	-0.01
			France	0.01	0.0023	0.002	0.00	0.02

Shapiro-Wilk: P>0.05

Test of Homogeneity of Variances: P=0.000

Welch ANOVA: Welch F(5,24.543)=187.190, P=0.000

The results reported in Table 1 demonstrate that the degree of leadership in the USA (Mean±SD: 0.31±0.0316), China (Mean±SD: 0.15±0.0468), Germany (Mean±SD: 0.08±0.0042), the UK (Mean±SD: 0.07±0.0035), France (Mean±SD: 0.04±0.0051) and Japan (Mean±SD: 0.05±0.0054) were significantly different according to the Welch ANOVA analysis (P = 0.00). The analysis of variance performed to compare each country pair of countries against each other shows statistically significant differences between all groups (P<0.05). It is worth highlighting that the mean leadership degrees of the USA outclass those of other countries. The difference between Germany, the UK, France, and Japan is relatively less than in Sino-US.

National impact according to leadership in research activities

The statistical result of the Impact of Papers based on Leadership (IPL) shows that the most influential country in research activities according to the dominance was the USA (Mean±SD: 1.18±0.0357), followed by China (Mean±SD: 1.18±0.0897), UK (Mean±SD: 1.04±0.0891),

Germany (Mean±SD: 0.88±0.0394), France (Mean±SD: 0.77±0.0428) and Japan (Mean±SD: 0.70±0.0446). The Games-Howell test results expose the multiple alignments of inter-country difference—the discrepancy between China and the US is minimal at 0.01, and is maximal at 0.48 between the USA/China and Japan. Most comparisons possess a marked significance (P<0.05), while the value of IPL does not present significant differences in the contrastive study of Chinese and American (Table 2).

Figure 2 shows the dynamic variation of the relationship between Leadership and IPL for each country. We can observe that the Leadership degrees of China and the United States have changed over a large span in the past decade, with the extreme deviation of Leadership in both China and the US exceeding 0.09, and China even exceeding 0.13, while Germany, the UK, France, and Japan do not in excess of 0.02. By contrast, despite the research impact of China and the United States being significantly above the world average level (IPL>1), it is the UK that holds the maximum range of the IPL (0.32), and China has occupied the second position (the extreme difference in IPL between 2012 and 2021 was about 0.25). The magnitude of research impact fluctuations in the last decade is similar in the United States and France, with the IPL having extreme differences of about 0.12. Nevertheless, it is noteworthy that among the six countries analyzed in this study, the dynamic changes of IPL have shown three trends: (1) overall volatile downward trends in the US and Japan; (2) an inverted U-shaped trend in China; (3) U-shaped trends in Germany, the UK, and France.

Pearson correlation analysis and Spearman correlation analysis were further performed to obtain the diversity of the relationship between Leadership and IPL among different nations. The statistical results indicate the existence of a strong positive correlation between Leadership and IPL in Japan (r=0.90, P=0.000) and the United States (r=0.84, P=0.002), a moderate negative correlation in Germany and the UK (-0.50≤r<-0.30) with no significant statistical results, a weak positive correlation in China (r=0.25, P=0.493) and a weak negative correlation in France (r=-0.17, P=0.642).

Table 2 Multiple Comparisons of IPL by country group based on ANOVA

<i>Descriptives</i>		<i>Dependent Variable: IPL</i>						
		<i>Multiple Comparisons: Games-Howell</i>						
<i>(I) Country</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>(J) Country</i>	<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>95% Confidence Interval</i>	
							<i>Lower Bound</i>	<i>Upper Bound</i>
USA	1.18	0.0357	China	0.01	0.0305	1.000	-0.10	0.11
			Germany	0.31	0.0168	0.000	0.25	0.36
			UK	0.14	0.0304	0.005	0.04	0.25
			France	0.41	0.0176	0.000	0.35	0.47
			Japan	0.48	0.0181	0.000	0.42	0.54
China	1.18	0.0897	USA	-0.01	0.0305	1.000	-0.11	0.10
			Germany	0.30	0.0310	0.000	0.19	0.40
			UK	0.14	0.0400	0.031	0.01	0.26
			France	0.40	0.0314	0.000	0.30	0.51
			Japan	0.48	0.0317	0.000	0.37	0.58
Germany	0.88	0.0394	USA	-0.31	0.0168	0.000	-0.36	-0.25
			China	-0.30	0.0310	0.000	-0.40	-0.19

			UK	-0.16	0.0308	0.002	-0.26	-0.06
			France	0.11	0.0184	0.000	0.05	0.16
			Japan	0.18	0.0188	0.000	0.12	0.24
UK	1.04	0.0891	USA	-0.14	0.0304	0.005	-0.25	-0.04
			China	-0.14	0.0400	0.031	-0.26	-0.01
			Germany	0.16	0.0308	0.002	0.06	0.26
			France	0.27	0.0313	0.000	0.16	0.37
			Japan	0.34	0.0315	0.000	0.23	0.44
France	0.77	0.0428	USA	-0.41	0.0176	0.000	-0.47	-0.35
			China	-0.40	0.0314	0.000	-0.51	-0.30
			Germany	-0.11	0.0184	0.000	-0.16	-0.05
			UK	-0.27	0.0313	0.000	-0.37	-0.16
			Japan	0.07	0.0195	0.019	0.01	0.13
Japan	0.70	0.0446	USA	-0.48	0.0181	0.000	-0.54	-0.42
			China	-0.48	0.0317	0.000	-0.58	-0.37
			Germany	-0.18	0.0188	0.000	-0.24	-0.12
			UK	-0.34	0.0315	0.000	-0.44	-0.23
			France	-0.07	0.0195	0.019	-0.13	-0.01

Shapiro-Wilk: USA, China, UK, France, Japan ($P>0.05$); Germany ($P=0.02$)

Test of Homogeneity of Variances: $P=0.006$

Welch ANOVA: Welch $F(5,24.901)=182.630$, $P=0.000$

Figure 2. Trends of the relationship between leadership and IPL in different countries (2012-2021)

International collaboration with leadership

The variables of ICL were first analyzed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilke test. The results showed that the data significantly deviated from a normal distribution in other countries apart from China ($PSW<0.05$). Therefore, we examined the differences in research cooperation among the national groups using the Kruskal-Wallis test (H).

According to the mean rank data reported in Table 3, France (39.8) had the highest level of scholarly international collaboration, followed by the United Kingdom (36.7), Germany (35.7), China (26.3), the United States (22.3), and Japan (21.3). However, the dynamic changes of ICL in the past ten years were not significantly different between the different national groups (PKW=0.074).

Table 3 Shapiro-Wilke test and Kruskal-Wallis test for ICL by country group

Country	Tests of Normality: Shapiro-Wilk			Kruskal-Wallis H Test			
	Statistic	df	PSW	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	PKW
USA	0.812	10	0.02	23.0	10.061	5	0.074
China	0.860	10	0.076	26.3			
Germany	0.821	10	0.026	35.7			
UK	0.822	10	0.027	36.7			
France	0.801	10	0.015	39.8			
Japan	0.809	10	0.018	21.5			

Figure 3. Trends of the relationship between leadership and ICL in different countries (2012-2021)

From the perspective of annual changes (Figure 3), the UK showed the highest increase, followed by France and Germany, and Japan showed the least increase. In parallel, we also observed that the variables of ICL in each country were lower than 5% in 2012, and the highest increase was heeded from 2015 to 2016, with the increase exceeding 150% in all countries except France. The ICLs presented varying degrees of reduction in each country in 2020 and rebounded in 2021. Remarkably, the degree of ICL in China continuously decayed from 2019 onwards. Notwithstanding the international collaboration situation started to ameliorate in 2021, the value of ICL remained considerably lower than that of 2019.

In terms of the relationship between Leadership and IPL, the correlation test found a substantial positive relationship in China ($r=0.65$, $P=0.041$) and significant negative correlations in other countries ($r<-0.5$, $P<0.05$).

Conclusion and discussion

In this paper, we explored the authentic effects of research leadership, scholar impact, and international collaboration at the country level from a bibliometric perspective, as well as their relationships and discrepancies.

The analysis of six major countries manifest the dominance of European and American nations in scientific leadership, albeit those tendencies are generally on the decline. In terms of national dominant scientific impact, the United States and Japan show similar trends of decrease, whereas China has experienced drastic change from rise to fall. The opposite was found for the expressions of the United Kingdom and Germany. The state-dominated international research collaboration exhibited similar patterns in all six nations—the ICL had increased slowly in the first 4 years, then rapidly rose in 2016 and decelerated in 2016, decreased quickly after 2019 and then rapidly increased again in 2021. Significant changes in national dominant scientific impact and collaboration were registered in the 2019–2021 compared to previous years in all countries.

Negative correlations were found between research leadership and country-led international research collaboration in developed countries with strong scientific research capability, which is consistent with the conclusions of the previous studies (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Dunning, 2015). However, the exact opposite occurs in developing countries like China. We found a high correlation between the rapid improvement of leadership and the expansion of national-led international research collaboration in previous years. The scientific isolationism and scientific systems consolidation requirements (Chinchilla-Rodríguez et al., 2019) can be reflected to a certain extent by the improvement of research leadership and the decrease in cooperation after 2018. Richard pointed out that political actions and tendencies in Europe and the United States have also contributed to the deterioration of the phenomenon (Richard, 2022).

Early studies have revealed the inverse relationship between the high citation of publications and research leadership (Bordons et al., 2015; Manganote et al., 2014), which is useful for developing countries (such as China) with the rapid development of science and technology and the resource-constrained developed countries in need of academic status consolidation. Our results show that the true effect sizes of research impact in countries with self-contained technology systems, such as the United States and Japan, are positively linked to the Leadership while Germany and the United Kingdom could not maintain this advantage. Limited resources and increased international competition for scientific research had led to a shrinking international share in those developed countries, which may have induced the expansion of research cooperation (Boekholt et al., 2009).

It is worth drawing attention to the dynamic variation of research leadership and state-dominated scholarly impact in emerging scientific nations. Figures 2 and 3 reveal an important relationship between these changes and the globalization of scientific research, and we can also note the high dependence of emerging developing countries on international collaboration. Emerging countries, especially those with rapid economic growth, abundant talent resources, and great potential for scientific and technological development, such as China and India, should pay more attention to how to enhance the global impact of their research based on

increasing the number of research papers, which is critical to sustaining their national position in the global scientific research system.

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